

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS.

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Annotation

It is possible to consider the development of communicative competence of teenage students as one of the methods of development and self-expression of participants of the educational process. Thus, communicative competence becomes one of the main parts of personal success, competitiveness and personal satisfaction, as well as high professional level, which depends on the quality of education. Active and effective listening and being tolerant is one of the main conditions of constructive communication.

Keywords: Competence, personal, tolerant, communicative, psychology, competent-active, education, professional education, social, professional, competence, skill, competence, modeling, communication.

In pedagogic textbooks and manuals, education is interpreted as a means of mutual cooperation between teachers and students and a means of mutual positive influence on each other. However, the socio-psychological system of this activity is not always taken into account. Here too, a number of problems arise that can negatively affect the content and methodical aspects of education and training. Mutual cooperation envisages social and psychological unity of teachers and students. In many cases, it is not paid attention to in the course of the lesson.

In the system of pedagogical communication of teachers of general education schools, the perception and thinking of one or another student is often formed in one mold, in the eyes of the teacher, they become an object of stable psychological communication. Therefore, if the student becomes "bad-behaved" in the eyes of the teacher, it affects the teacher's communication practice towards him.

In order for a teenager to have a healthy mindset, the content of individual characteristics in his way of thinking is of great importance. "The main reasons for the need to increase attention to the problem of adolescents:

- the influence of culture, art and literature, changing socio-economic conditions as a result of the development of science and technology;
- due to the expansion of mass media, the level of awareness of teenagers has increased;
- accelerated physical and mental development of adolescents;
- the necessity of a special approach to ideological-political, patriotic and international education when working with teenagers;
- the problems of transparency, social justice, and democracy are deeply penetrating the social life;
- a wide opportunity is created for students to learn independently, think creatively, self-manage, understand, evaluate and control. Therefore, the development of students' scientific

outlook and thinking leads to the development of communication culture and the formation of the skills of engaging in active relationships.

An important condition for modeling the future communication with students is the mutual emotional unity of the teacher and students, which gives the teacher the opportunity to foresee the following possible atmosphere of the lesson:

- to be able to anticipate various situations that may occur with a group of students in the upcoming lesson;

- - organization of various levels of democratic and free interaction with students, setting prospects for its development;
- - to create students' interest in learning and creative mood in the lesson.
- The development of communicative competence of teenage students can be considered as one of the methods of development and self-expression of the participants of the educational process. Thus, communicative competence becomes one of the main parts of personal success, competitiveness and personal satisfaction, as well as high professional level, which depends on the quality of education. Active and effective listening and being tolerant is one of the main conditions of constructive communication.
- It is very important to model future communication with teachers in the course of the lesson, because this process comprehensively determines the didactic principles of the lesson, directs the teacher to creative activity, in which he improves various models of communication in relation to the perfect forms of interaction with students. an opportunity arises.
- Communication modeling can be done quickly before a new lesson, and sometimes becomes permanent. It creates an opportunity for the teacher to foresee his communicative attitude and emotional behavior and feelings in the course of the lesson.
- Content of communicative skills:
- ☒ the ability to provide a social-psychological forecast of the communicative situation in which communication is established;
- ☒ social-psychological programming of the communication process based on the specificity of the communicative situation;
- ☒ implementation of social psychological management of communication processes in a communicative situation.

When talking with foreigners who have experience of communicating with young people from Uzbekistan, foreigners emphasize that our young people are ambitious, hardworking, have extensive knowledge in all fields, and that they have creative, free thinking, the ability to apply knowledge in practice, the needs of independent learning and They admit that it will be better if they pay more attention to the formation of their skills. Therefore, this issue is always reflected in all strategies aimed at ensuring the long-term development of countries. The Action Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the five priority areas of development in 2017-2021 also defined important tasks in this regard. It covers a number of priority tasks aimed at improving the effectiveness of state policy in relation to the youth, who are about eleven million citizens of Uzbekistan or 31% of the country's population. Therefore, the increase in the level of socialization among young people

stabilizes the social environment, the culture of communication and tolerance in relations develops in the society. The conditions and system of future communication will be determined, and a pre-planned communication model will be implemented. In the first moments of the communicative dialogue, the teacher should determine the possibilities of using the selected educational methods, feel the general mood of the students, their creativity and work ethic.

Today, in order to develop communicative competence in adolescents, it is important to improve the conditions and environment of the educational environment, as well as to ensure the development of communicative skills of the pedagogues themselves. The need to determine the criteria of the teacher's communicative competence made it possible to distinguish three levels of it: high, medium, and low.

A high level of communicative competence is characterized by a clearly expressed direction of humanistic interaction between the teacher and the students, in which both participants serve as subjects of this process, in which each of them is understood as a person and perceived as unique, irrevocable. In addition, the teacher feels the need to communicate with children and uses ethical forms of communication in practice. The teacher has significantly developed verbal and non-verbal communication skills, and there is no discrepancy between the verbal and non-verbal components of communication. The teacher knows how to regulate his psychological and physiological state. Uses a cooperative method as a way out of a conflict situation.

The medium level of communicative competence implies the insufficiently expressed value-communicative orientations of the teacher. Externally identified as humane, relations with students have the characteristic of fulfilling more social roles. Such teachers do not feel a special need for communication with children, the communication itself is strictly limited, often without positive emotional expressions. Verbal and non-verbal communication skills are significantly developed within the framework of professional necessity. The teacher knows how to regulate his psychological and physiological state, in this sense there may be certain emotional instability.

The low level of communicative competence among teachers was determined when they excluded one or several communicative values from their value orientations. Communication between a teacher and a student cannot be described as humane: students feel uncomfortable; the emotional aspect of the lesson is more negative; No contact with children. There is a discrepancy between the verbal and non-verbal organizer of communication in the teacher's behavior. The teacher often does not know how to regulate his psychological and physiological state.

Improvement of the education system and its quality, implementation of step-by-step consistent development in all areas of education is the foundation laid for the future. We all know that the result of the development of the educational system is an important factor underlying the socio-economic well-being of Uzbekistan. If we pay attention to the developed countries, their achievements and development are related only and only to high knowledge, aspiration and the factor of free activity and thinking created for young people. After all, "a teenager's claim to new rights, first of all, concerns the entire environment of interaction with adults. A teenager now begins to resist demands that he previously willingly complied with: when his independence is limited, when he is tutored, when he is directed, when he is controlled, when he is demanded to listen, when he is punished, when his interests,

relationships and thoughts are not taken into account, he is upset and resentful. means A teenager develops a sense of self-worth and considers himself a person who cannot be discriminated against or deprived of his right to independence. The type of relationship with adults in childhood changes, it does not correspond to his ideas about the level of his own size. He limits the rights of adults and expands his own. wants adults to respect their personality and human value, claims to show confidence and independence, that is, tries to achieve a certain equality with adults and their recognition of this. New norms of relations with adults are an important basis for forming a teenager's worldview regarding communication. An acceptable form of transition to a new type of relationship will occur only if the adults themselves take the initiative or take into account the demands of the teenager and change their attitude towards him. It is necessary to eliminate these relations through the organization of quality education, in the situation where teenage students are stubborn, insist on their own opinion, demand more freedom, move away from the family to the social environment and the circle of friends. it will be necessary to pay attention to the formation of skills such as the development of communication skills, establishing communication, establishing relationships, and to create a system of correct orientation of these problems in the pedagogical process.

The information society puts modern demands on us to increase the social activity of our youth. This, in turn, makes it more important to study and master international standards of training of competitive personnel and educate future specialists based on such principles. "Today, the pan-European standard requires the wide use of interactive and communicative methods. Therefore, it has become one of the urgent issues to use the experience of advanced countries to bring the education at all stages of the education system of our country to the level of world standards, to create new generation textbooks based on continuous and integrated State education standards. For this reason, fundamental reform of the educational methodology at all stages of education and raising it to the international level is being carried out step by step in our country.

The multifunctional field of social education is based on the following principles:

- consistency - aimed at revealing the integrity of the object and the mechanisms that ensure it, determining the various relationships of a complex object and bringing them to a single example;
- integrity-reflects the internal unity of the object, its relative autonomy, independence from the environment;
- subjectivity - includes consideration from the point of view of the student's ability to set and adjust goals, be aware of motives, independently implement actions and assess compliance with the plan, draw up life plans;
- integration - ensures integration of irregular events, parts, elements into a whole (orderly and structural).

Youth issues are closely related to education, morals, culture, health care, social relations, politics, law, religion, organization of free time, family, work, sports. Therefore, in scientific literature, these problems related to young people are studied both in the system of society and as a specific social group in a differential way. That is why there are cases of aggression, indifference, extremist moods and confusion among young people. In order to prevent this, it is important to improve their knowledge and skills regarding the correct distribution of their free time, as well as the formation of their communicative competence

and culture of communication. In this regard, people, "first of all, it is the most important task to form and educate the consciousness of young people on the basis of enlightenment. Of course, the implementation of reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies in order to take a worthy place in the international arena is a national development. is a priority aspect of our strategy".

The classification of three components and several parts, reflecting the important features of the educational system, is as follows:

a) includes the system of values, educational goals, educational principles, the vital content of the educational system, the methods of diagnosing and evaluating the results of this system, which are important for valuable subjects;

b) the spatial structure consisting of various forms and types of activities (individual, group, collective, frontal) is also developed by students in terms of self-organization and pedagogy;

c) coordination and pedagogical component, which is a set of pedagogical technologies of the educational process, the educational tasks of educational staff, the system of improving the professional competence of teachers, the system of pedagogical education and interaction with parents, education including managing the lim system.

Communicative competence of young people benefits in life classes, social relations and instability in society. Because social problems are eliminated on the basis of the enlightenment and communicative consciousness of the society and social sociability. It can be either productive for the society or a sign of limited, unstable, independence leading to the passivity of the individual. "The situation of principled equality of children of the same age arouses special interest in the adolescent in relation to this environment of relations, which corresponds to the ethical content of the feeling of personal greatness that arises in the adolescent. Adolescents develop values that are more understandable and closer to their peers than adults. Communication with adults cannot replace communication with peers. For a teenager, communication with peers separates into the environment of his personal relationships, where he acts independently. He thinks that he has a right to it, he defends his rights, and that is why the inappropriate and rude intervention of adults leads to resentment and dissatisfaction. On the one hand, a teenager clearly shows a desire to communicate with peers and to engage in cooperative activities. The desire to live in a community, to have close friends, is a strong desire to be accepted, recognized, and respected by friends. This is becoming an important requirement. The most unpleasant situation for a teenager is the displeasure of the team and friends, unwillingness to communicate, and the most severe punishment is open or closed communication, not talking. Important norms of the friendship code of teenagers are respect for honor, equality, loyalty, help to a friend, correct speech. Learning the norms of friendship is an important achievement of a child in adolescence. According to psychologists, "during youth, there is a need to express oneself, to be communicative, to realize oneself, to choose the field of self-realization and its methods, first of all, in the youth will give" . The ability of young people to control themselves, to analyze their life strategy, to study life perspectives is a necessity of life. This includes the following key indicators:

- problems that concern young people;
- feeling social;
- priority life values and plans;

- level of social maturity.

Assimilating the life experience of the older generation, teaching them the ways to benefit from work, and their training also have a positive effect on the communicative competence of teenagers. Social norms, values and wealth are the main socio-psychological managers and indicators of this process. It is these that determine the intellectual and practical activity of young people, the specifics of their problems, interests and expected results, self-management and management characteristics. At the same time, it shows the effectiveness of their social communication and the result of tolerant relations. "School and study occupy a large place in the life of a teenager. But despite the fact that they understand the importance and necessity of reading, different children look at this issue differently. For many, the fun of school is enhanced by the opportunity to interact with peers, but the learning itself is greatly affected by this. A lesson for a teenager is not only a 45-minute study, but also a situation of communication with classmates and a teacher, enriched with many important actions, grades, and experiences. With the transition to secondary school, the study of teenagers becomes significantly more complicated: instead of one teacher, there are five or six new ones, their way of explaining and asking, as well as their demands and attitude towards students different. In addition, teachers do not know them well at first, and as a result, there are "favorite" and "unfavorite" teachers. Adolescents are knowledgeable and demanding, but fair, open-minded and civilized, who can explain the material in an interesting and clear way, who can organize the lesson in a uniform manner, who can engage in it, and who can make the lesson maximally productive for each student. they like teachers. In middle grades, students begin to learn and master the basics of science. Children will have to acquire a large amount of knowledge. By the end of adolescence, they begin to think about their future profession and, in general, their future." So, on the basis of such an approach, building communicative competence in them, developing sociability, forming a culture of communication and tolerance in relations will benefit them in their future professional activities and social relations.

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